

On automation along the automotive wire harness value chain

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Abstract. An ambitious reduction of wire harness design time and cost by at least 50% each can only be achieved by automation. In the ITEA2-project IDEaliSM, it was demonstrated that the automation of 3D wire harness generation can be achieved using graph-based design languages and the VEC (vehicle electrical container) as an open data standard for wire harnesses. All the required data and process steps for generating the wire harness are described, as well as a wire harness assembly simulation.

Keywords: wire harness design, harness design automation, graph-based design languages, harness assembly simulation, harness value chain

1 Introduction

The wire harness represents to date the second most expensive part in a car and it is expected that its complexity grows even further. The associated value chain typically starts with the definition of the boundary conditions set by the original equipment manufacturer (OEM) with contractual specifications: A) the predefined electrical circuit diagram, B) the design space definition and C) the selection of dedicated components. It typically ends with the delivery of the designed and manufactured wire harness by the supplier to the OEM using just-in-time and just-in-sequence (JIT/JIS) logistics. Due to the high complexity and intensive coupling with other car parts only the design, manufacturing planning and organizational tasks have often remained in close geographic proximity to the OEM. Due to the price pressure in global competition, the manual wire harness assembly work has often been relocated to lower wage countries.

1.1 Current Wire Harness Design

The current status quo of wire harness design is a predominantly manual process chain and comprises the electrical and geometrical design process, which are performed concurrently. In the electrical design process an electric and electronic architecture solution is designed based on a choice of mechanical, electrical and electronic components, which need to be packed and routed inside a constrained installation space. In the geometrical design process in 3D, the OEMs usually provide the installation space as Digital Mock-Up (DMU) in a specific CAD data format. Positions of holes, tunnels, fixings, etc. can be derived from the DMU and serve as a part of the design requirements. The virtual 3D wire harness design is then typically created manually in a so-called “*cable workbench*” module in a CAD-system. Downstream, the wire harness manufacturing process steps lead to a full-scale 2D form-board plan for the manual wire harness assembly. Depending on the size and complexity of a wire harness, the entire development cycle may take up to 2 years and more (e.g. A380 wire harness).

2 Wire Harness Design Automation

During the manual process hundreds of design changes are likely to occur which need to be addressed in both process chains (geometrical and electrical) to avoid inconsistencies. In this section an automated approach to generate new wire harness designs is presented which is able to cope with these changes automatically.

2.1 Automation Approach

The automation approach based on graph-based design languages is a novel technology to model and execute design processes of complex systems incrementally. graph-based design languages possess a vocabulary, rules and a production system [8] and allow to encode the design knowledge of a product in a (re-)executable way. This know-how can be re-executed with changing customer requirements, which enables the generation of harness design variants and enables in this way a systematic exploration of the design space. This greatly accelerates the design, reduces the amount of errors, reduces time-to-market as well as costs.

Similar to programming languages, graph-based design languages require a compiler to be compiled (i.e. translated) into an executable model. In this project the Eclipse-based software *DesignCockpit43* (DC43) of IILS [10] was used to compile the graph-based design languages, which are modeled in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) as the underlying meta-model. While the graph-based design languages describe the use case, the generic (use case independent) automated harness design process described in section 2.4 is implemented in Java using Eclipse plug-ins for DC43. More information about the approach with graph-based design languages and DC43 can be found in the IILS white paper [10]. So far, graph-based design languages have been created for numerous engineering design and manufacturing applications, such as aircraft cabin design [9] and satellite design [4].

The wire harness design automation using graph-based design languages has been developed with the goal to be generically applicable to various cabling problems. This includes the ability to cope with highly detailed three-dimensional geometry. Various constraints have to be considered, like the physical properties of wires, restrictions for the placement and mounting, compliance to electro-magnetic interference, and clearances to hazardous areas like hot components. To overcome these challenges the approach makes use of advanced graph algorithms for pathfinding and collision detection. The automated wire harness has already been applied to several engineering domains ranging from the aerospace (launchers, satellites [11] and aircraft [9]) to the automotive domain (car cockpit wire harnesses [1]).

2.2 Use Case Car Cockpit

The example of an car cockpit wire harness shown here in figure 1 is the public demonstrator of the European ITEA2-project IDEaliSM [1].

The key goal of IDEaliSM in the automation of electrical wire harness design was to reduce the development time and cost by at least 50%, while still improving product quality. The solution developed with graph-based design languages generates the wire harness automatically, allows easy reconfiguration in case of different requirements and offers the capability to be embedded in an optimization loop.

In the IDEaliSM use case two versions of the cockpit are used, an industrial and an academic cockpit. The industrial cockpit with detailed geometry cannot be shown here for reasons of confidentiality. The academic cockpit variant [3] has a simplified geometry and was designed

Figure 1: Configurable Automotive Cockpit

to show various cockpit configuration variants which lead to variants of the wire harness. The configurable components, highlighted in blue in figure 1, include different shapes (i.e. instrument cluster and ventilation outlets), different topology (i.e. number of ventilation outlet and integration of the display) and optional components (i.e. head-up display, analog clock, air conditioner outlets). Depending on the selected configuration, the wire harness consists of about 50 connectors of 8 types and up to 196 single wires.

2.3 Data

For the automation of wire harnesses, three different types of data are required, which have to be provided for the use case and need to be combined in a graph-based design language: 1) master data, 2) geometrical components and 3) electrical schematics.

The master data describe the selected electrical and non-electrical components which interact with or are part of the wire harness, e.g. connectors, fixings, ducts, grommets, terminals, splices, wires, etc. A surface mesh geometry of the components is required for collision checking as well as “qualified” or “electrified” information for these components. A so-called qualified connector additionally contains the exact point and the direction where the wire bundle leaves the connector.

Figure 2: Qualified connector (left) and fixing (right) geometry

Figure 2 shows a such a connector (left) and a fixing (right). The geometry data can be imported via various formats like *stl*, *vtk*, *obj*, *stp* or *jt*. In the cockpit use case STEP files are used for the connector types. The additional electrical information for connectors and wire types (diameters, stiffnesses) was defined by a comma-separated values (CSV) file.

Geometrical Components of A) the installation space which constrains the wire harness and B) the instances of connectors, fixings, etc. are required. Since the master data already defines the geometrical representation of these components, providing their positions and orientations as well as a unique reference ID will be sufficient. Usually, a “cloud” of connectors and fixings defines the positions of these components, e.g. in an CAD assembly as STEP file.

Electrical Schematics data defining the connection list must be provided. As in this project, the connection list can be imported e.g. via an Excel or CSV file. The unique reference IDs of the two wired connectors must have the same reference IDs in the geometrical data world.

The data of the separated design processes for geometry and electrical architecture must be imported and merged. The combination of data is easily possible with graph-based design languages expressed in UML, since the designer can define his own data format with the help of the vocabulary of the graph-based design language. More convenient is the integration of a widely used XML-based data standard. With the Vehicle Harness Container (VEC) [2] such a data standard is available for the holistic description of a wire harness along its life-cycle. Our automated approach offers full VEC integration and uses only in-built extensions of the VEC.

2.4 Process

Our approach is divided into several separated steps. Each step reads the available VEC data, applies a specific task on it and writes back the result by modifying the data in the VEC model. The VEC model is thus enriched with each process step and the degree of completeness of the data is increased. In the following, each of the process steps 1 to 6 in figure 3 is explained.

1. Data Import. The first process step builds up the holistic model incrementally by executing the design rules of the graph-based design language. The input data described in the last section is read and imported to the VEC model. Since this step depends on the available type of data (i.e. file formats) a data importer created for a specific OEM can read the data from a specific set of file formats and link the data together. Data merging works properly if the reference IDs of geometry and electrical schematics match. Inconsistent or missing data can be identified by a consistency check which is executed directly after the import. After this step the model holds the connectivity data, the harness components and their respective master data specifications. Figure 3 shows the connectors in the design space which will be connected to a wire harness in the next steps.

2. Pathfinding. The pathfinding step can be characterized by finding the network topology of the wire harness by predefined sequential pathfinding tasks. This is done by using a logic to define the pathfinding sequence to generate the wire harness topology. A modified A* pathfinding algorithm finds the optimal paths on the discretized installation space between selected targets (e.g. path of connector A to a partial topology of the harness). In figure 3 the light blue areas are zones which are visited by the pathfinding algorithm. During this path search, a collision detection algorithm checks if the path is free from penetrations with the installation space geometry (i.e. the cockpit components) which serve as obstacles for the pathfinding algorithm. The topology and geometry of a wire harness is driven by the possibility where to attach the harness on the mountable structure geometry. In the cockpit use case, an intermediate topology of the wire harness is defined by waypoints along the cross beam, since it is possible to place fixings for mounting the wire harness there. To generate the final topology the connectors are routed to the intermediate topology via optimal paths.

3. Topology generation. This step collects the resulting paths from the previous task and assembles the network topology on which the single wires can be routed afterwards. The result is a topology which is mathematically a graph, represented by nodes (terminal points at connectors

and break-out points) and edges (harness segments between the nodes). The harness topology (shown in figure 3) is written into the VEC model as well as placement information for the connectors and optionally occurring fixings on the harness topology.

Figure 3: Automated wire harness design process steps 1 to 6

4. Routing. The routing step (see figure 3) routes the individual single wires on the harness topology created in the previous step. The routing is based on the shortest paths on the graph by minimizing cable lengths between the connectors which are connected by the wire. Inputs for this step are the topology, the harness components, contacting and placement information. When all wires are routed the diameters of the harness segments are calculated with a heuristic based on the information of included single wires and their types. The found routings for each wire of the connection list are added to the VEC model as well as the updated segment diameters.

5. *Multi-Body Simulation.* So far, the topology of the harness is defined, but the geometry consists of mostly rectangular geometrical paths. A multi-body physics simulation is performed to smooth the harness segment paths considering the different diameters and stiffnesses to produce realistic segment curvature and break-out points. Required minimum bending radii can be taken into account. Figure 3 shows the discrete mass points of the simulation represented as spheres which are connected by constraints. Again, a collision detection algorithm ensures that there are no penetrations with the installation space geometry during the relaxation process. The result is a realistic geometrical representation of the wire harness which is written to the VEC model.

6. *Data Export.* Since all harness data including the complete bill of material (BOM) is now available combined in a consistent model, it can be exported for downstream processes in form of an XML file conform to VEC or KBL (*Kabelbaumliste*, the preceding wire harness standard). For example, the generated geometry can be exported directly to various CAD systems where it can be used for installation space protection in the DMU (see figure 3).

2.5 Assembly Simulation

Before the wire harness is delivered to the OEM it must be ensured that the wire harness can be assembled into the constraining installation space. Some segments are long enough when the connectors are already plugged in, but must be lengthened to allow the connectors to be plugged in during integration. These segments can be automatically identified by performing the integration virtually in the simulation instead of a usual physical mock-up. A study of such an assembly simulation has recently been created [5] and applied to this use case for the assembly of a car radio into the foreseen slot in the cockpit. The multi-body physics simulation with collision detection mentioned before is used to ensure that the harness segments have sufficient lengths to plug the connectors.

2.6 Reduction of Design Time and Design Cost

The key goal of the ITEA2-project IDEaliSM [1] in the automation of electrical wire harness design was to reduce the development time and cost by at least 50%, while still improving product quality. Because of the fact that the exact savings identified in a dedicated campaign by industrial experts from the different project partners are strictly confidential, it can be clearly stated that the original claim of saving at least 50% was overfulfilled. As a further hint to a clear and full understanding of the true savings potential of the automation approach using graph-based design languages, a quote from the PhD abstract [4] is reproduced here: *“By the rigorous mapping of the design knowledge to a formal description, the consequent automated processing reduces the duration for a single . . . design to the execution times of the different algorithms. With regard to the chosen models and algorithms thus the theoretical lower limit for the duration of the design process is reached.”* Such significant savings are frequently reported in the literature [7].

3 Summary and Outlook

The wire harness development process has been successfully covered from the point where the electrical architecture is defined until the final virtual wire harness is available. That wire harness is collision free in arbitrary constraining geometry. The automated process steps are repeatable with individual input data, can be executed automatically and used in optimization loops. For example, if a design change makes adjustments necessary, e.g. due to an offset or relocation

of an equipment, the adjusted wire harness can easily be generated by clicking one button. The generation runtime of the described process in this use case was about 8 minutes on a regular desktop computer¹.

Along the wire harness life-cycle there are still some processes for automation conceivable. Upstream of the automated process, the electrical architecture must be designed. One task thereof is the decision about the grounding concept, i.e. splices have to be positioned. Downstream, before entering manufacturing, wire protections could be automatically selected and placed. For the manufacturing on a form-board, a harness flattening process is required for the form-board drawing. In the past, efforts were taken in digital factory simulations with graph-based design languages. This preliminary work could be applied to an envisioned future project, in which the manufacturing of wire harnesses with robots will be examined in a digital factory.

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¹Intel Core i5-2500K @ 3.3GHz with 32 GB RAM

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